

METHODS OF ORGANIZING ECOLOGICAL AND LEGAL PROMOTION WORKS IN THE SOCIETY BASED ON AN INNOVATIVE APPROACH

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Abstract. *This article aims to show that it is the main and legal duty of every person to protect the beautiful nature in its natural state and to promote it among the members of the society in an ecologically and legally correct way. In the process of propaganda, explaining that the light coming from the sun to our planet is of special importance in the life of living organisms, in turn, the adaptation of organisms to long and short cycles, the temperature usually changes a little faster in the dry part of the Earth, in the water. It is explained that along with the temperature, the humidity factor is also important in the spread of all organisms on the earth's surface. All these have been shown to be of great importance as an ecological factor. Some animals live by digging in the soil. By burrowing, winged birds and grasshoppers have adapted to lay their eggs in underground spaces. In the process of promotion, it was stated that such features should be promoted to every member of society and that they should follow ecological and legal norms.*

Keywords: *planet, sun, soil, humidity, water, night and day, ecological and legal promotion, birds, locust eggs, underground spaces, reproduction, their preservation and protection.*

In the **introduction** of the article, as long as a person lives in society, from the moment he steps into nature, to consciously use nature throughout his life, while carrying out ecological and legal promotion processes, the traditions, values, customs of our people who treats nature with respect and attention in terms of ethics and manners along with formation in every citizen, it consists of increasing natural resources, encouraging to organize gardens, flower gardens, awakening good qualities in people's hearts. Cultivation of an educated person who consciously understands the natural environment surrounding man and its resources, through ecological-legal propaganda, uses it sparingly in relation to nature, preserves it, contributes to the natural wealth and reproduction, knows social and natural laws - this is the ecological-legal propaganda is the main purpose. People who treat nature with respect and attention, notice and observe the positive and negative changes happening in every inch of their land, go to help nature, i.e. restore a fallen bush, fix a sick animal, treat it, try to clean dirty water, etc.

From this point of view, the topic we have chosen is the methods of organization of ecological and legal promotion work in the society based on an innovative approach. It should be the main duty of all the public to promote this issue in every way. Therefore, we will dwell on several environmental situations.

Turning to the **theoretical** aspects of the article, we will first of all focus on abiotic climate factors and light sources: Light is a type of energy consisting of electromagnetic waves coming from a light source. The light that comes to our planet from the sun plays an important role in the life of living organisms. Phototropism and photonastia observed in plants are important in providing the plant with sufficient light. Phototaxis plays a role in selecting a specific habitat in

unicellular plants and animals. It is one of the most important functions in the body. In humans, protective adaptations such as vitamin D synthesis, skin darkening. Behavioral actions such as avoiding direct sunlight.

A person sees rays with a wavelength of 0.40-0.75 μm . Short-wavelength rays are called ultraviolet, and long-wavelength rays are called infrared rays. It can be seen that living organisms use different wavelengths of the sunlight spectrum. Light is primarily needed for green plants. Under the influence of light, the most important physiological process, namely photosynthesis, takes place in green plants. In addition, light affects the biochemical and physiological processes in the cell, including the activity of enzymes, the synthesis of proteins and nucleic acids. It also affects the movement of leaf stomata, gas exchange and transpiration, etc. Plants can be divided into three groups according to their response to light.

1. Light-loving (heliophyte) plants. They can grow and develop normally only when there is enough light. Such plants include plants of the steppe, desert zones, sedges and some other species, tall trees that make up the first layer of the forest plant community, ephemeral life forms of short-vegetating perennial grasses in Central Asian conditions, etc.

2. Shade-loving (styophytes) plants. They are plants that grow in areas with strong frost. These include species growing in the lower layers of plant cover, mosses, ferns, and ferns. you can show wild henna and tolgunafsha growing under walnut groves. Light-loving and shade-loving plants differ from each other in their morphological, anatomic and physiological characteristics.

3. Shade-tolerant or facultative heliophyte plants. Although most of them are photophilous, they are species that grow and develop normally even when the light is not enough, and in excess light. They can include blackberry, white false strawberry, purple, black spruce and others.

If we pay attention to the practical aspects of the article, the nature of the alternation of day and night in different geographical areas is not the same. There is no difference between day and night around the equator. But in moderate (temperate) and cold climate zones, the day is long in the summer, the night is short, and vice versa in the winter. This, in turn, led to the adaptation of organisms to a long and short cycle (photoperiod). Among the northern plants, wheat, rye, spinach, sebarga, sorghum, sachratqn, gulsapsar, etc. develop normally in a long day, and buckwheat, khashargul, millet, sunflower, mavrak, tobacco, flax and others develop normally in a short day. Light plays an important role in the life of animals.

For example: a) light helps many animals fly and aim in space. It stops at a certain angle relative to the position of the feed with the sun. And birds, when flying to distant places, aim towards the Sun;

b) animals that live under sea and ocean waters, some beetles that live on land have the ability to emit light from their bodies. This phenomenon is called bioluminescence. This feature is common in everything from simple animals to fish.

c) light also affects the development of organisms.

Long-term exposure to light has accelerated puberty in insects and mammals; the kara-katitsa, which lives under the water, emits a liquid that illuminates the water to protect itself from the enemy;

Some insects stop reproduction as a result of the shortening of the day, and reproduction resumes with the lengthening of the day. The reason for this is that a long day affects the pituitary gland in the brain, increasing the work of the endocrine glands and also signals the gonads. Thus,

animals are divided into one group according to their attitude to light, such as light-loving, shade-loving animals, and groups adapted to light changes in a wide or narrow (short) range. Animals use light to see the surrounding creatures and aim around.

Temperature. Temperature is one of the factors that determine the distribution, reproduction and other life processes of organisms on the globe. At the equator, the temperature does not change drastically throughout the year and during the day. However, the temperature changes by 0.5-0.6° every 100 km in the direction north or south of the equator. Such changes occur every 100 m in the mountainous part of the land. Therefore, the life processes of all plants and animals are related to these changes. Such changes play a special role in the spread of plants. For this reason, when studying the plants found in the flat part of the Earth and the cover they form, they are divided into several climatic zones, such as: Arctic, tundra, forest, steppe, desert, subtropical and tropical geographical zones. Plants are studied in two large ecological groups according to their adaptation to low or high temperature.

The temperature usually changes quite rapidly in the dry part of the Earth. And in the water environment, such changes change very slowly, especially during one day. In general, most living organisms live between 0° and 50°C. When the temperature is below 0° or above 50 C, all life processes stop completely or slow down dramatically. Therefore, the life of living organisms is affected by the optimum, minimum and maximum temperature.

Moisture. Along with the temperature, the moisture factor is also important in the distribution of all organisms on the earth's surface. It is not wrong to say that there is no life without water. Water exists in nature in many forms, such as rain, snow, fog, sleet, dew, and ice, all of which represent the concept of moisture. However, we believe it is better to use the term water instead of moisture.

Water makes up 50-98% of the substances in the plant body. All biochemical reactions in cells take place with the participation of water. Water is also important for aquatic organisms. In places with a lot of precipitation on the earth, daily precipitation reaches 1000 mm at the most (Charapundji), and in the Sinai desert it is only 10-15 mm. No precipitation is observed in the Peruvian and Aswan deserts.

Hydatophytes - this group, whose life is always spent in water, mainly includes algae. Hydatophytes are plants whose body part is outside the water and the rest is in the water layer. This group includes water lilies, sedges, sedges, sedges, and other aquatic flowering plants. They are often found in river and lake banks, swamps, dense forests and mountainous regions. Hygrophytes also have the same characteristics as hydrophytes, adapted to conditions of excess moisture.

Mesophytes are plants that live in moderate moisture conditions. This ecological group includes many cultivated and wild plants.

Xerophytes are plants adapted to living in arid conditions. They are widespread in the steppe, desert and semi-desert zones. Xerophytes, in turn, are divided into two groups: sclerophytes and succulents.

Moisture or water also plays an important role in the life of animals. In general, animals satisfy their need for water in three ways:

- 1) By drinking water directly.
- 2) By eating plants.

3) Metabolism, the process of breaking down fats, proteins and carbohydrates in the body. Evaporation of water is done mainly through breathing, sweating and urination. On hot days, some mammals may spend too much water. Thus, animals living in arid conditions replenish the water lost from their bodies with the water released during the breakdown of proteins, fats and carbohydrates, which is considered a complex process, through the whole body - through sweat through the skin layer or through food. Animals living in water - hydrophiles (dwellers in water and on land, earthworms, gastropod mollusks, molluscs) can live only in very humid conditions. Mesophiles are moderately water-demanding, that is, eugenic organisms that tolerate changes in humidity well.

Air is a mixture of gases in the atmosphere, and its composition changes depending on the change in altitude. Air is important not only as a habitat for organisms, but also as an ecological factor. Almost 50% of the plant's dry weight is carbon absorbed from the air. Clean and dry air in the atmosphere contains 78.1% nitrogen, 21% oxygen, 0.9% argon, 0.03% SO. In addition to these, small amounts of radioactive substances such as neon, helium, krypton, xenon, ammonia, hydrogen, radium and thorium, as well as various nitrogen oxides, chlorine and other elements are found. If this indicator decreases by 5%, it becomes difficult for organisms to breathe. Carbon dioxide gas is almost constant, and only in large cities its amount can be excessive. It is known that carbon dioxide gas is important in nutrition for green plants. Despite the large amount of nitrogen in the air, organisms cannot absorb it directly. Organisms can absorb it only in combination. Nitrogen serves as a source of nutrients for nodule bacteria, azotobacteria, actinomycetes and blue-green algae. Changes in the amount of nitrogen in the air depend on human activity or the nature of the vegetation cover. Sulfite anhydride, nitrogen oxides, hydrogen halides, ammonia, etc. contained in the air are harmful substances and cause its pollution. They enter the plant body during air feeding of plants, precipitation, fog. Plant leaves and cells that have absorbed such toxic substances in the air begin to die. The water-absorbing mechanism of the trees fails and the leaves are woven. And the top branches dry up. Thus, air flow (or wind) has a mechanical, biological (physiological, anatomical, morphological), geographical and other impact on the life of all living organisms.

Soil. Soil refers to the porous, fertile surface layer of the earth. Soil is the outer layer of rocks that has changed naturally as a result of the combined action of water, air and various organisms. The main characteristics of the soil as an environment for the organism include its natural and chemical composition and the circulation of substances in it, that is, the circulation of gases, water, organic and mineral substances in the form of ions. is also the cause.

Soil is home to plants, microorganisms, and some invertebrates. For example, 1 sq.m. 100 billion simple animal cells, millions of nematodes, hundreds of earthworms, hypha-mycelia of 100 thousands of fungi, bacteria and algae live in the soil layer. Therefore, all living organisms found in the soil affect each other in different ways, that is, as a result of complex relations between plants, animals and microorganisms, humus and mineral substances accumulate in the soil.

Plants that show the richness of the soil in certain chemical elements are called indicator species. In addition to bacteria, fungi, simple animals, worms and arthropods are widespread in the soil. Granularity of tuiroq particles is also ecologically important for animals. Some animals live by digging in the soil. Insect larvae cannot live in rocky soils. Hummingbirds have adapted to lay their eggs in underground cavities, and most grasshoppers have adapted to lay their eggs in

porous soil. Light is not very important for animals that live underground. The temperature in the deep layers of the soil does not change.

In **conclusion**, it can be recognized that many facts can be expressed about the current state of the soil. It must be said openly that the ecological situation in the territories of all the member republics of the Commonwealth is not very good. The condition of the soil is especially bad in the lands that are engaged in agriculture. Therefore, it is the sacred duty of all people today to protect all natural areas, to organize ecological and legal promotion work in society based on an innovative approach.

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